

Quantification and Reduction of Cross-Section-Induced Uncertainty in a Micro Reactor Using Critical Experiments

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ABSTRACT

The impact of nuclear data uncertainty on a 1 MWt output, trailer-transportable, solid-moderated, and solid-cooled micro reactor concept is addressed. The two main objectives are: (1) to quantitatively evaluate the uncertainty in neutronic characteristics parameters caused by nuclear data, and (2) to demonstrate how existing critical experiment data can be used to effectively reduce these uncertainties. In this study, core analyses were performed using the continuous-energy Monte Carlo code MCNP. A data assimilation approach was employed to reduce nuclear data-induced uncertainty using a critical experiment database. As a result, the 1σ standard deviation of the uncertainty in the effective multiplication factor (k_{eff}) was reduced by nearly half, from $0.53\%\Delta k/k$ to $0.28\%\Delta k/k$, through data assimilation of nuclear cross-sections based on the critical experiment database. However, no reduction was observed in the uncertainty associated with the nuclear data of BeO. To reduce this uncertainty, the addition of critical experiment data that is not included in the existing Whisper database is considered. However, since the sensitivity coefficients of these additional data considerably differed from those of the micro reactor, they may not be effectively used in the data assimilation process. If so, new experimental data with high sensitivity coefficients of BeO similar to those of the micro reactor will be necessary.

Keywords: Micro-reactor, graphite moderated, uncertainty quantification, uncertainty reduction, MCNP/Whisper

1. INTRODUCTION

Accurate prediction of reactor core performance is essential for the safe and economical operation of nuclear reactors. Numerical simulations are used to predict the neutron behavior of a reactor core. Based on these predictions, neutronic characteristics parameters—such as power distribution and core lifetime—are calculated. The reactor design is then optimized so that these nuclear characteristics meet safety and economic design criteria.

The micro reactor [1] considered in this study is one of the innovative reactor concepts currently being developed to address diverse modern energy demands. Due to its extremely compact core size compared to conventional light water reactors (LWRs), the micro reactor offers high transportability and the potential for complete factory fabrication. That is why it is expected to serve as a power and heat source for areas where disasters occur, remote islands, and isolated regions [2].

The target micro reactor is designed as a solid moderated/cooled reactor that eliminates liquid coolant from the core to prevent loss-of-coolant accidents (LOCAs). This design approach results in significant differences from conventional LWRs in terms of geometry, core materials, and neutron energy spectrum. Consequently, it is difficult to directly apply operational experience and analytical methodology developed for existing reactors, and the uncertainty associated with numerical simulations is expected to be larger. This will be a design challenge, as the reactor's actual operation behavior may deviate from predictive calculations. Prediction accuracy is important since micro reactors rely on a digital twin system that utilizes real-time simulations rather than direct nuclear instrumentation as in existing reactors [2].

To address these challenges, this study aims to quantitatively evaluate the prediction uncertainty of k_{eff} that arises from nuclear data. The target system is an all-solid-state, solid-moderated, and solid-cooled

micro reactor, whose thermal and electrical outputs are 1 MWt and 300 kWe, respectively. The target core diameter and core length are approximately less than 1 m and 2 m, respectively. The reactor employs high-assay low-enriched uranium (HALEU) fuel enriched to 19.75 wt% in ^{235}U and is expected to sustain full-power operation for more than ten years without refueling.

The present study has three main objectives. First, to make a detailed micro reactor model and perform analyses by the continuous-energy Monte Carlo code MCNP [3] to calculate the k_{eff} and cross-section sensitivity coefficients. Second, to evaluate the prediction uncertainty of k_{eff} and its breakdown using Whisper code [4]. Third, to assess the potential for reduction of prediction uncertainty of k_{eff} caused by nuclear data through the incorporation of existing critical experiment data from the ICSBEP [5].

The following sections are organized as follows. Section 2 explains the evaluation methodology of sensitivity coefficients and cross-section-induced uncertainty, and the calculation geometry. Section 3 presents the results of the core neutronic analysis, the evaluation of the cross-section-induced uncertainty on predicted k_{eff} , and the uncertainty reduction achieved through cross-section adjustment. Finally, Section 4 summarizes the conclusions of this study.

2. ANALYSIS METHODOLOGY AND TARGET CORE SYSTEM

2.1. Analysis Methodology

The continuous-energy Monte Carlo code MCNP6.3 is used to calculate k_{eff} . The Whisper code was employed to evaluate the uncertainty originating from nuclear data and to assess the uncertainty reduction achieved through cross-section data adjustment using existing critical experiment benchmarks.

The k_{eff} of the micro reactor was calculated by using MCNP6.3, and the validity of the computational model was confirmed by comparing the result with a reference value calculated by the continuous-energy Monte Carlo code MVP [6], as reported in the literature [1]. The reference value is limited to three significant digits since it was directly read from the graph in the reference [1]. The nuclear data library used in this study was ENDF/B-VII.1. A total of 10,000 histories \times (100+500) batches were simulated, where the first 100 batches were treated as inactive cycles and excluded from tally evaluations. ENDF/B-VII.1 was used because Whisper code (v1.1) does not support the latest ENDF/B-VIII.0 or ENDF/B-VIII.1 libraries.

The evaluation of cross-section-induced uncertainty and the cross-section adjustment were performed by using the Whisper code. Similar considerations were conducted for high-temperature gas-cooled reactors using the Whisper code [7]. Covariance data with a 44-group structure, provided with the Whisper code, were utilized. Consequently, the sensitivity coefficient of k_{eff} was also determined in 44 energy groups. In Whisper code, the correlation coefficient (C_k) between the target system and benchmark critical experiments is converted into a weighting factor, and nuclear covariance data adjustment is performed using benchmark experiments [8]. The benchmark critical experiment data used in this study were those included in the Whisper code or taken from the ICSBEP database.

The cross-section data assimilation in Whisper code is performed using the Generalized Linear Least Squares (GLLS) method, which adjusts the cross-sections to minimize the bias between experimental and calculated k_{eff} values while accounting for the uncertainties in both cross-sections and experimental data [8]. Finally, the uncertainty of the target system after cross-section adjustment is calculated using the adjusted nuclear data covariance and the sensitivity coefficients of the target system. In general, performing cross-section adjustment is expected to reduce both the prediction bias and the associated uncertainty. In the present study, the adjusted covariance data in the Whisper code are used.

2.2. Target Core System

The analysis target is the micro reactor core under conceptual design [1]. In this core, Tristructural-isotropic (TRISO) fuel of 1mm diameter, enriched to 19.75 wt% uranium-235, is employed. This TRISO fuel is packed into cylindrical fuel compacts with a radius of 0.5 cm made of a SiC matrix, with a packing fraction of 60%. The structural material of the core is high-oriented graphite blocks (HOGBs) [2], which

can be used as a neutron moderator; it possesses both lightweight properties suitable for portability and high thermal conductivity. Cylindrical fuel compacts are loaded into the HOGBs moderator blocks with a pitch of 5 cm.

The cylindrical fuel compacts containing TRISO fuel were modeled as a honeycomb lattice arrangement, in which the TRISO fuel is distributed in a triangular lattice. To reduce the computational time, the coating layers of the TRISO fuel and the SiC matrix of the fuel compacts were homogenized based on the volume ratio. The effect of this homogenization on the k_{eff} is confirmed to be sufficiently small. Similarly, the emergency safety shutdown system and the heat transfer tube located in the peripheral and central regions of the core were also homogenized with the HOGBs, assuming a volume ratio of 2:1. Although the effect of these simplifications on the calculation results has not been evaluated, it is inferred that they do not significantly affect the primary objective of this study, which is to quantify the cross-section-induced uncertainty and its reduction through data adjustment.

Control drums are placed outside the core to control reactivity by changing their rotation angle. The three analysis cases considered in this study are summarized in Table I. Additionally, the core cross sections are shown in Figures 1 to 4. Cases (1) and (2) were selected to determine the reactivity worth due to the rotation of the control drums, whereas Cases (1) and (3) were selected to evaluate the effect of the BeO reflector in the control drum on the k_{eff} . Figure 1 shows the axial cross section of the core, which is common to all models. Figure 2 shows the radial cross section for Case (1), in which the absorber region of the control drums faces outward. Figure 3 shows the radial cross section for Case (2), in which the control drums are rotated 180° from Case (1). Finally, Figure 4 shows the radial cross section for Case (3), in which the BeO reflector in the control drum of Case (1) is replaced with HOGBs.

Table I. Analysis cases.

Case name	Absorber orientation	Materials of the control drum
(1) Positive reactivity position (Materials: B ₄ C + BeO)	Outward	B ₄ C + BeO
(2) Negative reactivity position (Materials: B ₄ C + BeO)	Inward	B ₄ C + BeO
(3) Positive reactivity position (Materials: B ₄ C + HOGBs)	Outward	B ₄ C + HOGBs

Fig 1. Axial cross section.

Fig 2. Radial cross section of Case (1).

Fig 3. Radial cross section of Case (2).

Fig 4. Radial cross section of Case (3).

3. NUMERICAL RESULTS

Table II presents the calculated k_{eff} values of the models at 1200 K with the corresponding reference value [1]. The statistical errors in calculated values are less than 0.05 %dk/k. These are small enough to be neglected compared to the cross-section-induced uncertainty. Although some parameters, including the core size, material composition, and temperature, are not completely identical, the difference between the calculated k_{eff} values and the reference k_{eff} value is small. These results demonstrate that the micro reactor model was properly constructed.

Table II. Calculated k_{eff} of micro reactor core.

Case	Reference value [1]	Calculated k_{eff} value
(1)	1.17	1.17
(2)	0.874	0.879
(3)	1.13	1.13

Table III and Table IV present the ten largest contributors to cross-section-induced uncertainty of k_{eff} (1σ standard deviation) before and after the cross-section adjustment.

Table III. Top 10 contributors to cross-section-induced k_{eff} uncertainty (before assimilation).

Total nuclear data-induced uncertainty(1σ)		0.53%
Nuclide	Reaction	Standard deviation [%]
U235	Neutrons per fission (ν)	0.30%
U235	Neutron capture	0.21%
C	Elastic scattering	0.20%
Be in BeO S(a,b)	Elastic scattering	0.16%
O in BeO S(a,b)	Elastic scattering	0.16%
U235	Fission spectrum	0.15%
U235	Fission	0.13%
C	Neutron capture	0.08%
U238	Neutron capture	0.07%

Table IV. Top 10 contributors to cross-section-induced k_{eff} uncertainty (after assimilation).

Total nuclear data-induced uncertainty(1σ)		0.28%
Nuclide	Reaction	Standard deviation [%]
Be in BeO S(a,b)	Elastic scattering	0.16%
O in BeO S(a,b)	Elastic scattering	0.16%
C	Elastic scattering	0.11%
U235	Neutrons per fission (ν)	0.07%
U235	Neutron capture	0.07%
Graphite S(a,b)	Elastic scattering	0.05%
Be9	Neutron capture	0.04%
C	Inelastic scattering	0.04%
U238	Neutron capture	0.03%

By using critical experiment data, the cross-section-induced uncertainty of the k_{eff} (1σ standard deviation) is reduced from $0.53\% \Delta k/k$ to $0.28\% \Delta k/k$, approximately halving the uncertainty. Furthermore, the k_{eff} increased by 1.0% due to the cross-section adjustment. Among the critical experiment data used for data assimilation, leu-comp-therm-060-005 and leu-comp-therm-060-006 [9] in the Whisper database have the highest Ck value. These critical experiments are RBMK-type reactors that are graphite-moderated, light water-cooled, with low-enriched uranium fuel. Since the micro reactor also uses graphite moderator and uranium (HALEU) fuel, these critical experiments had the highest Ck values among all experiments. However, Ck values of these experiments were still below 0.7. This indicates a lack of critical experiment data with highly similar sensitivity coefficients.

Almost all nuclear data uncertainty was reduced by about half, but no reduction was observed in the uncertainty associated with the nuclear data of BeO, which is used in the control drums.

The number of critical experiment data that include BeO is limited in the critical experiment database embedded in the Whisper code. Consequently, the cross-section adjustment for BeO nuclear data could not be effective as for nuclides such as uranium, for which a larger amount of benchmark data is available. To address this issue, new sensitivity coefficients from the ICSBEP report can be added to the benchmark experiment database in the Whisper code. For example, the benchmark experiments such as heu-comp-mixed-003-001 to heu-comp-mixed-003-006[10] and U233-met-therm-001-001[11], which have a sensitivity coefficient of BeO, are available in the ICSBEP Handbook but are not currently included in the benchmark experiment database in Whisper.

Figure 5 shows the U235 fission sensitivity coefficients for the micro reactor model, the candidate critical experiment (heu-comp-mixed-003-001) to add to the benchmark experiment database of Whisper, and the model having the highest Ck value in the existing Whisper database.

Fig 5. Sensitivity coefficients of U235 fission

The peak energy range of the sensitivity coefficient for the candidate experiment differs significantly from that of the micro reactor, resulting in low Ck values.

Similarly, Figure 6 shows the sensitivity coefficients of Be in BeO elastic scattering for the micro reactor model and the candidate critical experiment (heu-comp-mixed-003-001).

Fig 6. Sensitivity coefficients of Be in BeO elastic scattering

A significant difference in the shape of the sensitivity coefficient is evident. The calculated C_k value between the micro reactor and heu-comp-mixed-003-001 was 0.08. Similar calculations were performed for the other candidate benchmark experiments, but their C_k values remained low, reaching a maximum of only about 0.2. Because the sensitivity coefficients of Be in BeO are nearly zero, the effectiveness of these candidate experiment data is unclear, but the incorporation of these data might improve the uncertainty of BeO.

In this study, the value of cross-section-induced uncertainty was reduced by assimilation. A further reduction in uncertainty might be expected when the sensitivity coefficient data from the ICSBEP report are incorporated into the benchmark experiment database in the Whisper code. If the incorporation of these critical experiment data is not effective, performing new critical experiments using BeO or validating the TSL data for BeO through measurement of the neutron decay constant α will be an effective approach for reducing the nuclear data-induced uncertainty of the micro reactor.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, the cross-section-induced uncertainty in a micro reactor was quantitatively evaluated, and the uncertainty reduction through data assimilation using critical experiment data was investigated. The target micro reactor is an all-solid-state reactor with core thermal output of 1 MWt. Graphite is used as a moderator and structural material, and TRISO fuel containing HALEU enriched to 19.75 wt% uranium is used. The analysis was performed using the continuous-energy Monte Carlo code MCNP6.3 and the Whisper code.

Through cross-section adjustment in the Whisper code, the cross-section-induced uncertainty (1 σ standard deviation) was reduced by approximately half, from 0.53% $\Delta k/k$ to 0.28% $\Delta k/k$. However, the BeO-nuclear-data-induced uncertainty of the k_{eff} was not reduced. Therefore, the addition of sensitivity coefficient data containing BeO nuclear data from the ICSBEP report to the benchmark experiment database in the Whisper code is considered. On the other hand, in the ICSBEP database, few critical experiments containing BeO are dominated by reactions in the thermal energy region. Therefore, the uncertainty of BeO may not be sufficiently reduced, remaining a major contributor to the overall uncertainty. If this is the case, conducting new critical experiments using BeO or validating the TSL data for BeO measurement of the neutron decay constant α are expected.

In further work, when effective critical experiment data containing BeO is available, those data will be added to the critical experiments database used by Whisper code, and we will confirm whether the cross-section-induced uncertainty is reduced or not. Additionally, the impacts of cross-section-induced uncertainty at different temperatures on the calculated k_{eff} , should be considered.

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